

ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN – THE BASIS OF A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

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Annotation: This article talks about the importance of ensuring gender equality, significant work is being done in Uzbekistan to further strengthen the legal foundations of ensuring equality between women and men in all areas. Today, the issue of ensuring gender equality has risen to the level of state policy. This is considered one of the advanced steps in the field of human rights of our country.

Key words: gender, gender equality, increasing the role of women, women's rights, oppression, violence.

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В НОВОМ УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ – ОСНОВА УСТОЙЧИВОГО БУДУЩЕГО

Аннотация: В данной статье говорится о важности обеспечения гендерного равенства, в Узбекистане проводится значительная работа по дальнейшему укреплению правовых основ обеспечения равенства женщин и мужчин во всех сферах. Сегодня вопрос обеспечения гендерного равенства поднялся на уровень государственной политики. Это считается одним из передовых шагов в области прав человека нашей страны.

Ключевые слова: гендер, гендерное равенство, повышение роли женщины, права женщин, угнетение, насилие.

INTRODUCTION

Gender issues play an important role in the development of human civilization and regulation of production processes. For this reason, from the past to the present, the topic of gender equality has always been a hot topic of discussion.

Ensuring the equality of gender issues, increasing the role of women in society and expanding their opportunities in public administration, developing entrepreneurship and ensuring social protection of women is a priority in every state policy. Today, great work is being done in Uzbekistan to ensure the rights and interests of women, to create decent working and living conditions, to realize their potential, to form a strong civil society, to ensure the rule of law and to protect their legal interests. As a result of the wide-ranging reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a solid legal basis was created for the issues of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men in all spheres of public life and activity, and protecting women from oppression and violence.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

In the Universal Declaration of Human Rights adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 10, 1948, gender equality is an important part of international law in the field of human rights. In this document, the rule that “all people are born free and equal with their dignity and rights” is of particular importance. Due to the lack of equal rights between women and men, girls and boys in history, women's socio-economic and political rights have been violated for a long time. 1979 The General Assembly adopted the 30-article Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women. The Convention clarified what is meant by discrimination against women and proposed a national effort to end such discrimination on the

agenda. Also, it is noted that culture and traditions are a force influencing the family and ensuring gender equality. This document is the first human rights treaty confirming women's reproductive rights. The issue of gender equality has been raised to the level of state policy, and 25 legislative documents related to the field have been adopted.

Formed in the years of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legislation regulating political and economic spheres, created legal and organizational mechanisms in all areas of society evidence of choosing a policy to ensure equal gender opportunities gives [1].

RESEARCH RESULTS

Uzbekistan began participating in the list of gender equality indicators from 2019. As of 2019, Uzbekistan ranked 62nd among 189 countries in the list of gender equality indicators [2]. The reforms carried out in the field had a positive effect on the place of our country in international rankings, and in 2020, the World Bank's Women, Business and Law Index included the Republic of Uzbekistan among the 27 countries that implemented important reforms in terms of women's rights and gender equality, and increased by 5 places to 190 countries. took 134th place among.

As a result of the attention paid to women in our society, the conditions created for them to get education, choose a profession, work, and show their talent, today our women are active in all aspects, in a word, their social and political activity is increasing, and the number of potential women is increasing. expanding[3]. As a result of the reforms carried out to increase the role of women in public administration in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the share of women in the management staff was 28.2 percent. In particular, 24% of senators, 33% of deputies of the Legislative Chamber, 25% of deputies of the Dzhokorg Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, People's Deputies of regions and Tashkent city councils are women. According to UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres, "when women take leading roles in society, executive and legislative bodies will be more responsible"[4].

DISCUSSION

Today, more than 240 women are working in executive positions of executive power bodies of the republic and local level. Also, in order to further increase the share of women in public administration, a special program was developed and focused on implementation. Within the framework of the program, a reserve of more than 25,000 women with management potential in various fields was formed. In order to ensure the rights and interests of women and girls, to effectively implement the state policy on comprehensive strengthening of the family institution, a vertical system was created that penetrates to the lowest level - neighborhood and household. The position of women's activists was introduced in about 10,000 neighborhoods. The participation of women in the decision-making process has increased significantly. I consider it appropriate to quote President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis in June 2019: "... today every woman should not be an ordinary observer, but also an active and proactive participant in the democratic changes taking place in the country"[5].

The processes of increasing the economic-political and socio-legal activities of women in the society are considered to be a demand of the time that cannot be delayed. The issue of women is inextricably linked with society, social relations, nations, states, culture and civilizations [6].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of legal documents have been adopted on the issue of ensuring gender equality and women's rights and increasing their opportunities. Decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on ensuring women's rights, in particular,

on gender equality and protecting women from violence and oppression, on strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship development, are important documents aimed at ensuring gender equality in our country. Uzbekistan has adopted a strategy to achieve gender equality by 2030. The main goal of the gender strategy is to ensure real equality of women and men, regardless of race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, faith, personal and social status.

The main tasks of the gender strategy are:

- expansion of women's ownership of land and property;
- to support women's equal participation with men in all spheres of society's life and activities, including politics, economy, law, culture, education, science and sports, and to create equal opportunities for them to take the lead in decision-making;
- increasing the political activity of women, changing the negative views related to their place in society;
- Guaranteed equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the field of employment, as well as creation of decent jobs, development of women's entrepreneurship, expansion of women's opportunities to receive loans from commercial banks;
- to encourage women and men to study throughout their lives, to increase their medical culture in family planning and to strengthen their reproductive health, to promote a healthy lifestyle among them;
- creation of effective organizational and legal mechanisms for combating human trafficking and forced labor, preventing oppression and violence, identifying and eliminating them;
- strengthening the family, increasing the responsibility of all family members in family relations, preventing early marriage, marriage between close relatives, early childbirth and family separation;
- budget planning, integration of gender issues into budget processes, improvement of gender statistics in promotion of the principles of gender equality, equal implementation of rights and opportunities of women and men;
- implementation of comprehensive measures to improve Uzbekistan's position in international rankings and indexes assessing gender equality, women's entrepreneurship, oppression and violence against women and men;
- Increasing the role of parliament, civil society institutions and media in achieving the national goals of ensuring gender equality in the field of sustainable development and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women until 2030.

CONCLUSION

It is noteworthy that in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, serious attention was paid to the issues of treatment of women in state and community management, creation of decent living conditions for women, systematic study of their problems, promotion of work and entrepreneurship. Because it is important that in the sixth point of this Petition: further strengthening of the role and position of women in state and society management is recognized as one of the most priority directions of our reforms.

Today, it is becoming more evident that gender equality is of urgent importance in social relations, which are important for the development of society. As a result of paying special attention to increasing the activity of women in the family and society, especially in social life, great changes are being made in social relations and legislation. Along with the results achieved in terms of creating equal conditions for women, there are still many issues that are still waiting to

be resolved. For example, increasing the attractiveness of entering the public service and the convenience of the work regime for women, ensuring the competitiveness of women in the labor market, creating favorable conditions for harmonizing the responsibilities of the family in raising children, providing quality medical services, and eliminating existing gender stereotypes in the promotion of women from the career ladder. the era itself demands.

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